

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D9.10 - Scientific dissemination summary report project

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D9.10) outlines COVINFORM’s scientific dissemination activities carried out over the course of the project. This deliverable builds on and updates the Dissemination Plan (D9.1) published in M1 and the M18 update of the Dissemination Plan (D9.6).

The overall dissemination strategy used, devised as part of the COVINFORM project, focuses on defining the *what*, *when* and *how* we will convey key messages and outcomes of the project to stakeholders, and who the stakeholders are. The strategy outlined how the consortium aimed to engage with stakeholders in order to assure the uptake of the project results to assure a more intersectional pandemic response in the future.

The dissemination plan outlined activities to publicly disclose the results of the project through various means including through scientific publications. These activities are much more focused on the results of the project and, thus, will also be used to exploit the COVINFORM results and raise users’ interest in using project outcomes. The dissemination plan includes:

- Objectives and strategy.
- Key target groups and key messages relevant to the project.
- Dissemination channels and tools such as articles in specialist journals, presentations at external workshops and conference papers, which are also important activities to ensure the transfer of knowledge and results of the projects and, thus, to encourage external stakeholders to adopt these results.
- Dissemination activities such as the networking events and webinars which will be used to encourage dialogue and bilateral exchange of ideas and knowledge between practitioners, decision- and policymakers, suppliers and academia.
- Dissemination management policies, including a timeline for the planned activities.
- Evaluation and monitoring processes of the dissemination activities, including key performance indicators (KPIs).

This deliverable is complemented by D9.2 (Communication plan), which focuses on the communication to the general public and the use of specific media (e.g., social media, press). Although these channels will be used for the dissemination of COVINFORM’s results, they will also be used to engage and raise awareness of the general public about COVINFORM.

Revision notes M36

We have reviewed the Dissemination Plan and found that the strategy chosen to meet the project goals was still relevant and appropriate. In addition to some editorial corrections throughout the document, several updates were made to reflect the state of the project and its dissemination progress. The summary of those changes can be seen further below and are marked in the different section with the “M36 Updates” heading.

Overall, the project has met, and in some cases, exceeded the expectations of efforts towards dissemination. The active and effective collaboration between partners led by TRI and SYNYO has resulted in the majority of KPIs achieved by M36 (see Table 6). Finally, all the dissemination activities carried out so far were recorded in Annex 6.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1 Acronyms and abbreviations

Term	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GA	Grant Agreement

1 Introduction

COVINFORM aimed to holistically assess the social, economic, and political impacts of the COVID-19 crisis focusing on government, public health, and citizen responses and the role of (mis-)information and communication during all stages of the pandemic. The project also examined how European governments define and address vulnerability to COVID-19, if at all. COVINFORM partners developed solutions, guidelines, and recommendations to mitigate health inequalities and improve the wellbeing of the most vulnerable individuals.

COVINFORM employed data from:

- a cross-analysis of pre-existing studies on national, regional and local levels to map the responses and assess the impact of the pandemic,
- relevant dimensions of health, socioeconomic, political, and community vulnerabilities.

The project culminated in the development of an online portal and visual toolkit for stakeholders in government, public health, and civil society integrating data streams, indices and indicators, maps, models, primary research and case study findings, empirically grounded policy guidance, and creative assessment tools. The results will provide a unique combination of new enabling technology along with a set of guidelines and best practices aligned with the EU standards and legislation.

Recap of the COVINFORM Dissemination Strategy

1.1 Objectives

The objective of COVINFORM's dissemination strategy was to raise awareness about the project and its results. In this plan, we will identify and organise the activities to be performed in order to promote the widest dissemination of knowledge from the project in order to promote the uptake of COVINFORM's results and tool components. As such, the strategy is expanded in two directions:

- Towards engaging with key stakeholders (e.g. decision-makers, public health officials, medical practitioners), the EC and general public to inform them about the project and its results.
- Towards paving the way for exploitation and enhancing the potential of the results and how end-users can use them to their benefit.

1.2 Strategy

The dissemination activities were carried out in three main phases, spanning throughout the project duration and extending beyond it, with increasing levels of intensity, starting from the creation of general awareness and concluding with attracting potential supporters and customers/users of the project results. As a result, our dissemination efforts included three phases:

- **At the start of the project:** drafting the dissemination plan; definition of the expected impact; consideration of how and to whom the outcomes will be disseminated. The condition of the call was for the project to produce some initial outputs already by M3, ready to be disseminated and communicated
- **During the project:** updating the dissemination plan with recent information on the project and results; conducting regular activities such as workshops and webinars, etc.; assessing the impact on our target groups; involving other EU projects and various stakeholders in view of transferring results to end users.
- **After the project:** continuing further dissemination; developing ideas for future cooperation; evaluating achievements and impact; engaging in marketing-related activities.

COVINFORM used different channels and means for dissemination, including:

- Online dissemination (e.g. project website, social media accounts, podcasts, webinars, and multimedia materials)
- Non-electronic dissemination (e.g. scholarly articles in specific journals, brochures and other printed materials)
- Interactive dissemination (e.g. workshops and conferences)

1.3 Key Target Groups

Dissemination is crucial for COVINFORM research to ensure exploitation of the results and achieving the desired impact. In order to succeed in raising awareness of our findings, the right stakeholders need to be identified. Moreover, choosing the right target audiences for dissemination paves the way for exploitation, given that our project stakeholders will be interested in, and can benefit from our findings, results and solutions. The goal was to engage with at least 100 stakeholders from at least 6 different countries, not limited to the EU.

Decision-makers, Policymakers, NGOs, international organisations, national planners and public authorities:

Decision-makers responsible for public health management and communications in pandemics were the main target of COVINFORM, at a local, regional, national, EU, and international level. Decision-makers are held accountable to ensure that measures are taken in the direction of mitigating the impact of the pandemic on the general population, so their involvement in the project is crucial. As the vaccination programs continued in Europe, communication still played a core role in governments' responses to COVID-19. It was crucial to ensure that hygiene COVID-19 measures and guidelines are kept up while the vaccination programs are rolled out and to counteract vaccination hesitancy and scepticism. Policymakers in the field of pandemic crises preparedness and response were another target of COVINFORM.

Medical practitioners, first-line practitioners, healthcare workers, care workers:

Acknowledgement of their potential to minimise the negative impact of the pandemic on the society as a result of their role within the health system is essential to ensuring that appropriate prevention and treatment are in place. First responder organisations, such as SAMUR and MDA, were at the heart of the COVINFORM consortium and an important piece of the value chain in the battle against infectious diseases, and thus one of the priority target audiences of the COVINFORM dissemination strategy.

Researchers and Academia:

Interacting with academics and researchers throughout the project duration led to insightful feedback and discussions that positively influenced the development of the tools and recommendations. Furthermore, academics and researchers further disseminated the work of COVINFORM within universities and training environments, therefore reaching potential end-users. In doing so, we also aimed to interact and exchange ideas with other research consortia working on COVID-19 and its consequences, funded by European funds and other financing channels. This has increased the triangulation of the results and the interdisciplinary nature.

The results generated by COVINFORM will have a major scientific impact on academic and research partners through the publications of papers in high quality peer-review journals and edited volumes, dissemination of findings in international and local conferences and provision of networking opportunities via meetings and seminars that will lead to further research initiatives. The outputs will further enhance all research partners' interdisciplinary research in the areas covered by the project which will lead to improved national and international visibility, increased collaboration with the industry and will attract greater numbers of high calibre students for both undergraduate and postgraduate courses in universities.

Civil society and vulnerable individuals (i.e. women, children, older people, persons with disabilities, individuals from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, migrants, ethnic minorities, Indigenous peoples, volunteers)

Citizens were also targeted by the COVINFORM communication activities. As the civil society's wellbeing has been heavily affected by the coronavirus pandemic, it is important that they are aware of the EU funded activities and research that are being undertaken to develop better governmental response strategies. As a part of WP6, empirical research was carried out on COVID-19 impact amongst communities across the EU. Thus, engaging with citizens through dissemination activities was particularly important for COVINFORM.

Our stakeholder list and network was continuously updated throughout the course of the project and categories of stakeholders are not intended to exclude any potential stakeholder in the project.

1.4 Building a network

Building a contact list: In order to have a contact list that is relevant to the project and our dissemination and communication goals, we have leveraged the partners' contacts as well as collected publicly available ones, based on the legitimate interest principle. The partners each provided a list of contacts from stakeholders across the EU, (including the media) using public information and contact information that they have obtained from previous collaborations and believed may be relevant to COVINFORM as well. We used email addresses that have either been given to partners directly by the stakeholders themselves (thereby giving their consent to be contacted via that email address) or organisation email addresses that are publicly available. Contact details were also gathered by networking with potential stakeholders at events or through personal collaborations, in which case informed consent to receiving communications was obtained. By the end of the project, in October 2023, the list contained 371 stakeholders.

All personal information collected in COVINFORM's contact list was managed and used in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

- On the basis of informed consent (GDPR Art. 6.1.a):
 - People subscribed to the COVINFORM newsletter via the Moosend Signup Form embedded in the COVINFORM website.
 - People who expressed their interest in the COVINFORM project (participation in workshops, in touch with the individual partners, etc.).
- On the basis of legitimate interest (GDPR Art. 6.1.f):
 - Project information can be sent without prior consent to the business email addresses that appear on public websites of organisations, companies, ministries, universities, etc.

A legitimate interest assessment form has been developed and has been confirmed with the DJUST at the EC as the lawful basis that can be used to collect stakeholder lists within EU projects. On the basis of this assessment form, COVINFORM follow the process below:

- Collect relevant business contacts (e.g. organization emails xxxxx@trilateralresearch.com as opposed to personal emails, e.g.XXXX@gmail.com)

- In each communication sent from COVINFORM channels, contacts will have the option to opt-out from any other future communication (for example when sending the newsletter, they will be provided with an unsubscribe option)
- In the project's [Privacy Policy](#), we will specify how the consortium is going to use these contacts and that these contacts will be used only within the remit of the project and not repurposed for other usage.

1.5 Key messages

In the table below we present key COVINFORM stakeholder groups, the means and channels we will use to engage with them, and the targeted key messages.

Table 2: Target Audiences and Key Messages

Target Audience	Key messages	Key channels and activities
Decision-makers, Policymakers, NGOs, International Organisations, national planners and public authorities	<p>COVINFORM is developing a toolkit and policy recommendations to ensure that the needs of vulnerable and marginalised groups are appropriately considered in potential further waves of COVID-19 and future pandemics.</p> <p>COVINFORM will review behaviour change theories (e.g., theory of planned behaviour, Protective Action Decision Model) and identify communication strategies that different stakeholders – especially governments and public health authorities – can implement to (positively) influence the behaviour of individuals, groups and, communities within their social and cultural contexts that influence the extent and speed of behaviour change.</p>	<p>Website, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials, webinars, workshops, demonstrations, policy white papers, policy recommendations.</p>
Medical practitioners, first-line practitioners, healthcare workers	<p>COVINFORM will examine public health systems, including long term care infrastructures, to understand effects and impacts of the crisis, including those on vulnerable groups such as frontline healthcare workers. As part of the project’s intersectional approach, COVINFORM will pay particular attention to women who are the majority of healthcare workers.</p>	<p>Website, social media, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials, webinars, journal articles, workshops, demonstrations</p>
Researchers and Academia	<p>COVINFORM will contribute to knowledge in the field by identifying strengths and weaknesses of current responses and communication strategies employed by national planners and healthcare decision makers but also add scientific knowledge on how pandemics impacts the lives of vulnerable groups.</p> <p>The research we are developing in this project will improve knowledge in the sector and will be useful to researchers in the field.</p>	<p>Website, social media, newsletter, printed materials, webinars, journal articles, workshops, conferences, demonstrations</p>

Target Audience	Key messages	Key channels and activities
Civil society and vulnerable individuals	COVINFORM will identify the impact that national, regional, and local COVID-19 responses have had on human behaviour, social dynamics, and physical and mental health outcomes within both general populations and specific vulnerable groups. It will examine the impact of social distancing and lockdown measures in terms of social isolation and time spent indoors, and the disruption of work/school-life balance.	Website, social media, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials
Media and general public	<p>COVINFORM is identifying and analysing strategies for inclusive and effective COVID-19 communication and to prevent misinformation, disinformation, malinformation, 'fake news' and conspiracy theories.</p> <p>It will examine how the shift to digital communication has potentially excluded several (already vulnerable) groups from communication and relevant information, potentially increasing their vulnerability.</p> <p>It will examine further the possibilities to fight misinformation and conspiracy theories (e.g., regarding vaccinations), deriving recommendations and lessons learned.</p> <p>Finally, it will provide guidelines for representation and justice of different (vulnerable) groups in the media.</p>	Website, social media, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials

2 Dissemination channels and tools

2.1 Project website

Figure 1: Screenshot of the COVINFORM website

The project website (<https://www.covinform.eu/>) is the main online tool for public dissemination and communication and serves as the main point of contact for the project. Its structure allows the consortium to tailor communications for different target audiences as the project progresses.

The website provides visitors with a brief overview of COVINFORM project and the consortium, featured news, and a section describing research conducted and expected impact. It was developed in M1 (November 2020) and is continuously managed by SYNYO. As a communication tool, it was also described in deliverable *D9.2 Communication plan*. It is maintained and updated regularly (e.g. at least once a month) throughout the project's lifecycle.

The project website also features the COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository (Task 8.6), launched in M2. The repository draws together COVID-19 resources that were identified as relevant for government and public health representatives, CSOs, NGOs, policymakers, and citizens. It integrates the useful outputs of WPs 2-8: the project parameters, data flows, research findings, case study assessments, and response guidance. It includes resources designed to improve the resilience, wellbeing, and mental health of the population, frontline workers, and, in particular, of the most vulnerable groups. The Knowledge Repository holds three sections of content:

- Communication & Misinformation (<https://www.covinform.eu/knowledge-repository/communication-misinformation/>)
- Models & Data sources (<https://www.covinform.eu/knowledge-repository/models-data-sources/>)
- Events (<https://www.covinform.eu/event-directory/>)

Newsletters, blogs, videos and project outcomes such as reports, videos, and whitepapers are posted on the website (and on social media) as they become available to provide up to date and relevant information. Partners contribute by writing blogs that will be featured in the news section of the website and to actively promote them to the various stakeholder communities. This contributes to raising awareness about the project's results by increasing traffic on the website and enhancing opportunities for networking, forging collaborations and ultimately, exploitation.

The blog planning schedule is a rough outline, it is flexible and can be adapted, based on the needs of the project (e.g. important developments in the pandemic, participation in events or other unforeseen opportunities that we may want to promote) and the availability of results. Partners are always welcome to provide us with suggestions, and we also plan to publish public-friendly articles about COVINFORM outcomes.

M36 Update

The table below describes the blog publishing schedule from M1-M36 of the project. In comparison to the original proposed scheduling of an average of 1-2 blog posts produced per month, the consortium published a total of 42 blog posts. The blog topic variety covers issues related to the pandemic in general, but also reports on the progress of the COVINFORM project. In addition, the consortium partners are active in contributing to the content management of the COVINFORM blog. The blog review process established by TRI and supported by SYNNO guaranteed cohesiveness between stylistic writing, good readability and relevancy with the overall dissemination strategy of the COVINFORM project.

Table 3: Blog schedule from M1-M36

Number	Topic	Partner	Published
1	COVINFORM: Project on social, behavioural and mental health-related issues kicked off	SYNNO	24/11/2020
2	Understanding vulnerability through dialogue: two-way dialogue and inclusivity in COVID-19 communication	TRI	21/12/2020
3	First lessons learned from COVID-19 vaccination in Spain	SAMUR	22/01/2021
4	COVINFORM at the COVID-19 2C sister project meeting	TRI	01/02/2021
5	Quarantine – history repeated	SYNNO	22/02/2021
6	Why gender matters in the COVID-19 response	SYNNO & TRI	08/03/2021
7	The COVINFORM team – supporting gender equality in EU Research and Innovation	SYNNO & TRI	08/03/2021
8	Red Cross in the COVID-19 pandemic – how Romania handled the outbreak	SNCRR	17/03/2021
9	The COVAX Facility: the way forward to ensure equitable distribution of COVID-19 vaccines?	UANTWERPEN	01/04/2021

Number	Topic	Partner	Published
10	Tackling COVID-19: collaboration for better results	TRI	15/04/2021
11	Joining forces in mitigating risks of the COVID-19 pandemic	TRI	07/05/2021
12	What is the Pandemic Teaching? Vaccines in a changing economic and social context	SAPIENZA	27/05/2021
13	Timely, transparent, targeted? Government communications during the pandemic		21/06/2021
14	One size does not fit all – information seeking during the COVID-19 pandemic in a segregated society	UGOT	07/07/2021
15	Red Cross in the COVID-19 pandemic – how Austria handled the outbreak	AUTRC	02/08/2021
16	Government and the pandemic: structures and response	KEMEA	18/08/2021
17	18 months of COVID-19 pandemic in Germany	SINUS	10/09/2021
18	COVID-19 and mental health: a ‘tsunami’ of problems?	UANTWERPEN	06/10/2021
19	Pandemic mitigation for everyone: Ethnic differences in Wales	SU	23/11/2021
20	Generation COVID	SYNYO	10/12/2021
21	Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories	MDI	20/12/2021
22	“Can we at least freak out?” Memes and COVID-19	SAPIENZA	22/02/2022
23	Nobody told us what to expect (except health professionals and our own simulations)	FS	16/03/2022
24	Italy in lockdown: The ultra-secular battle of laughing to avoid crying	SAPIENZA	13/04/2022
25	"Un-masking the Mask-Issue": Examining People's Sense-Making Processes and Risk-Cultural Norms regarding Facemasks	UGOT	27/04/2022
26	Summer holidays 2022: may the COVID be with you (hopefully not)	URJC	19/08/2022
27	Monkeypox in the time of COVID-19: Are we on our way to a new pandemic?	TRI	30/08/2022
28	New crises, same resilience?	SINUS	18/10/2022
29	Has COVID-19 changed our cities? Urban planning following the pandemic	UANTWERPEN	28/10/2022
30	Compulsory vaccinations and skipping contact restrictions – differing narratives of freedom in the German middle class	SINUS	07/12/2022

Number	Topic	Partner	Published
31	Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?	TRI	18/12/2022
32	"Bridging the gap": The importance of interpersonal risk and crisis communication	UGOT	31/01/2023
33	Let me explain: why we use intersectionality and complexity theories	FS	18/04/2023
34	How COVID-19 has exposed housing inequalities: insights from Antwerp	UANTWERPEN	21/06/2023
35	Policy and practice mismatches in governmental responses during the COVID-19 pandemic	KEMEA	26/07/2023
36	Delivering inclusive and accessible COVID-19 communication in Birmingham (UK)	TRI	17/08/2023
37	Understanding the Systems we Live in: Deconstructing the Systems we Live by	FS	28/09/2023
38	Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part 1	SINUS	20/10/2023
39	Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part 2	SINUS	24/10/2023
40	The Challenges of Understanding Covid-Related Risk: Part A	TRI	25/10/2023
41	The Challenges of Understanding Covid-Related Risk: Part B	TRI	27/10/2023
42	Three Years of COVINFORM: A little glimpse into what we have done	SYNYO	31/10/2023

2.2 Website visits

M36 Update

Visits to the website were monitored throughout the project lifetime to keep track of the number of visitors and evaluate the effectiveness of dissemination. The original KPI set out in the Dissemination Plan (see D9.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan) was that the COVINFORM website will have had 4,000 unique visits by M36. By M18, 4,588 unique visits were recorded, thus surpassing the KPI by M18 instead of M36. Given the successful accomplishment of the KPI, a new KPI was set in the revisited D9.6 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (M18) to increase the unique website visits to at least 5500 by M36. By M36 the unique website visits reached 22,466, which surpasses the updated KPI by more than 5 times. In addition, the website had 29,063 views.

2.3 Newsletters

The partners set out to produce a newsletter every four months containing items on pandemic response management and other topics covered by the project (e.g., wellbeing during the pandemic, means of countering misinformation) arising from our research and posted on the project website, as well as news related to other projects and sources, events, and dissemination materials (e.g., videos), including key publications.

The newsletters were tailored to fit with COVINFORM's visual identity (graphics are embedded into Moosend to create an appropriate template for distribution) which makes them easily recognisable by the stakeholders who receive them, thereby strengthening the project brand and the impact of our dissemination activities.

We created an initial Moosend contact list based on the project's stakeholder and media lists (which will then get populated on an ongoing basis), thus sending the newsletters to those who we believe may have a legitimate interest in receiving news about our project or stories related to pandemic management and the other topics covered by the project. Readers will, of course, be able to opt out if they no longer wish to receive our newsletters. The newsletters were also published on the project website and on social media for a wider dissemination.

The consortium aimed to have 500 individuals/organisations signed up to receive the newsletter by M24 and 600 total by the end of the project in M36.

M36 Update

The COVINFORM project has produced nine newsletter issues during its lifecycle. This is following the above-outlined plan, which describes the aim to send out a new newsletter issue every four months. Furthermore, all newsletter issues are published on the COVINFORM website (see here: <https://www.covinform.eu/resources/newsletter/>), so the audience can revisit all the previously published newsletters. Once a newsletter was published, it was also shared on COVINFORM's social media platforms to increase the possible reach and encourage the audience to subscribe to the newsletter. The content of the newsletter aimed to inform the readers about the latest news, publications, and project activities. Newsletter issues also included relevant news from the PREPARE cluster projects (see ***Collaboration with other EU Horizon 2020 Projects*** section for further reference) to promote cross-project collaboration and engage readers in interesting events and news. By M36, there were 371 individuals subscribed to the COVINFORM newsletter. It did not meet the target KPI of 600 individuals/organisations subscribed to the newsletter. However, all newsletters are also available on the project website in a separate section. The website had 29,063 views and 22,466 unique visits, which surpasses the KPI by more than 5 times. Moreover, we assessed that this tool for dissemination reached its capacity with the numbers that we achieved and therefore we increased our efforts for dissemination through other channels, like social media, events participation and presentations, and publications of bi-monthly reports, blog posts, and other project outputs directly on our website.

2.4 Conferences

Conference attendance is a key mechanism for the COVINFORM consortium to interact with the scientific and industrial community. Through presentations and papers, the consortium members will disseminate information regarding work carried out in COVINFORM. In parallel, by attending conferences and exhibitions the consortium members will have the opportunity to get an

understanding of current technology trends, so that project activities can be fine-tuned during the project's lifetime. COVID-19 travel restrictions may affect the format of some conferences, particularly at the start of the project, and we will adapt to these formats where necessary. It is expected that some conferences will be transferred to online events, and we will participate in this way. We will still be able to attend and give presentations at these events and an online event may be accessible for a larger pool of people to attend.

Each consortium partner should aim to present at minimum one conference (at least 2 conferences for research partners) or participate in networking activities with pertinent EU and national projects.

M36 Update

Partners presented finding from the project at a total of 24 conferences and attended another 11 conferences and other scientific events in addition. See Annex 1 for a full list of conferences and events attended by the COVINFORM consortium.

2.5 Events (physical and virtual, e.g., webinars)

By presenting project outputs at networking events, meetings and conferences, COVINFORM creates synergies with other projects and encourages up-take of the solutions by the end users. Additionally, COVINFORM will involve stakeholders in project activities to gain their feedback on project outputs. By involving these stakeholders, COVINFORM will ensure that the project results are fit for purpose and meet the needs and requirements of end users, thus ensuring their successful uptake. COVINFORM will also showcase its outputs as providing an effective solution and thus, encourage external stakeholders to use them themselves, outside of the project's activities.

M36 Update

COVINFORM partners attended and presented the project updates and results at multiple conferences, workshops, and other events. They participated or attended a total number of 37 events, including webinars, workshops and other events. Annex 1 provides the overview of all activities related to event participation.

2.6 Workshops organized

A minimum of three workshops (virtual or face-to-face) will be held at the beginning, mid-point and end of the project as a part of WP2, the aim of which is to develop the risk assessment model to evaluate the response and impact at different geographical levels. The purpose of the workshops is to gain end-user input, identify and assess relevant datasets, indicators and models, and to evaluate and further refine the risk assessment model for COVINFORM with relevant project partners and end users. During the workshops, we will gather feedback from stakeholders and engage with them to influence the outcomes of the project. The workshops will seek to explain the extent to which the risk assessment model assists users in identifying relevant factors that shall be considered to identify and tailor intervention measures for different countries/regions; evaluating the effectiveness and impact of different responses, and improving responses.

M36 Update

COVINFORM partners organized 6 workshops. MDI and SAMU organized two COVINFORM workshops together, one of them with 2 sessions, and the other one with 3 sessions. SNCRR organized one COVINFORM workshop, with 8 sessions. See Annex 1 for a detailed list.

2.7 Publications for peer-reviewed journals or edited volumes. Publications non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed

COVINFORM partners will collectively aim to publish a minimum of 10 articles and 10 external blogs based on project activities and results.

M36 Update

As of M36, partners published or submitted a total of 18 scientific texts. There are 7 published journal articles, and 6 published book chapters. In addition, 1 journal article is in revision, and another 2 journal articles have been submitted to peer-reviewed journals. 2 scientific papers have been published online. Annex 1 (Publications, scientific for peer-reviewed journals or edited volumes peer-reviewed section) shows the current list of published and submitted articles in peer-reviewed journals.

As far as the external blog articles are concerned, COVINFORM project partners wrote and successfully published 13 publications in outlets different than the project website (see Annex 1, Publications (not peer-reviewed or non-scientific)).

2.8 White papers, policy briefs, fact sheets, country reports

As described The COVINFORM project will publish white papers, policy briefs, fact sheets, and country reports that will build on the outcomes from WPs 4-7 and provide guidance and recommendations in relation to government and policy (WP4), public health (WP5), the citizen response (WP6) and communication and misinformation (WP7). They will be aimed at engaging policy makers and decision-makers in discussions about the project outcomes.

M36 Update

The COVINFORM website includes the Project Outputs page, where outputs are published divided in categories (<https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/>). The COVINFORM project has published 3 whitepapers, 10 policy briefs, 5 fact sheets, and 11 country reports.

Topic	Partner	Published
White papers		
INCLUSIVE COMMUNICATION IN TIMES OF CRISIS: lessons learned and recommendations from COVID-19 and other CBRNe incidents based on recent COVINFORM & PROACTIVE findings	Anson, S. (TRI), Bertel, D. (SYNYO), Havârneanu G. (UIC), & Petersen, L. (UIC)	2021

Topic	Partner	Published
White paper on public health responses during the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons learnt and recommendations for policy makers	Robinson H., Van Caudenberg R. & Van Praag L. (UNIANTWERPEN)	2023
Leveraging Public Momentum During a Crisis: Recommendations for Policy and Practice	Tautscher I. & Edwards J. R. (SINUS)	2023
Policy briefs		
COVID-19 Governmental responses and challenges: The case study of low socio-economic status citizens in Greece	Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Ioannis Konstantopoulos, Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA)	2023
Addressing Vulnerability and Promoting Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems: A case study comparative analysis of the COVID-19 Pandemic throughout Europe	R Beatriz Rosa, Benjamin Trump, José Palma-Oliveira, Igor Linkov (FS)	2023
Healthcare policies during the pandemic: Preventing the spread of COVID-19 or inequality?	Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin (SU)	2023
STRUCTURES, INSTITUTIONS AND ACTORS IN THE RESPONSE TO THE COVID-19 CRISIS IN SPAIN: Challenges, dilemmas and proposals.	Javier Lorente, Manuel Tamayo, Isabel Bazaga, Irene Sánchez-Vitores, José Luis Postigo, Antonio Rodríguez. (URJC)	2023
ESTRUCTURAS, INSTITUCIONES Y ACTORES ANTE LA RESPUESTA A LA CRISIS DE LA COVID-19 EN ESPAÑA: Retos, disyuntivas y propuestas.	Javier Lorente, Manuel Tamayo, Isabel Bazaga, Irene Sánchez-Vitores, José Luis Postigo, Antonio Rodríguez. (URJC)	2023
Community mental health responses for migrants to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic in Antwerp	Jil Molenaar, Hannah Robinson & Lore Van Praag (UNIANTWERP)	2023
The impact of COVID-19 on marginalized groups in Greece	Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Ioannis Konstantopoulos, Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA)	2023
Healthcare workers during the pandemic: lessons learned and the way ahead	Daniela Foresta, Elena Ambrosetti (SAPIENZA)	2023
Policing during COVID-19: The impact of Coronavirus on Law Enforcement Agents	Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Ioannis Konstantopoulos, Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA)	2023
Micro-politics of agency taken by residents living in Antwerp's as a consequence of COVID-19.	Hannah Robinson, Jil Molenaar & Lore Van Praag (UNIANTWERP)	2023

Topic	Partner	Published
"Community" in times of crisis: Perceptions of low-SES women in 10 EU countries (WORKING TITLE)	Isabella Tautscher and James Rhys Edwards (SINUS)	2023
Fact Sheets		
COVINFORM workshop for responders	SAMUR & MDA	2023
Emerging vulnerabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic: Findings from the COVINFORM project	TRI	2023
EFFECTIVE AND INCLUSIVE CRISIS COMMUNICATION DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: LESSONS LEARNT	SYNYO	2023
Media literacy and COVID-19	MDI	2023
Pandemic communication: How can we reach the most vulnerable?	AUTRC	2023
Pandemie Kommunikation: Wie erreichen wir vulnerable Gruppen?	AUTRC	2023
Country reports		
Public health responses Country reports: Greece	KEMEA	2021
Baseline Austrian Response	AUTRC	2023
Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot	SU	2022
Opinions on Test, Trace, Protect and COVID-19 vaccination services by BAME and White people in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot	SU	2023
Government responses to COVID-19 and vulnerability in Wales	SU	2023
The COVID-19 pandemic in Wales: Public health governance, preparedness, and vulnerability	SU	2023
Crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic in Wales	SU	
The multiplicity of BAME migrant nurses' vulnerabilities in South Wales	SU	2023
Swedish Baseline Report: Public health responses	GU	2023

Topic	Partner	Published
Public Health Response Austria: COVID-19 Pandemic	AUTRC	2023
Management and Response of the Covid-19 Pandemic: Austria in Focus	SYNYO	2023

2.9 Collaboration with other EU Horizon 2020 Projects

COVINFORM will link with other similar EU- funded practitioner networks, including but not limited to the ones listed in the table below. We will reach out to the different projects to discuss and to identify mutually beneficial opportunities to disseminate and exploit the findings from each project.

M36 Update

Since the beginning of the project, the COVINFORM consortium has been active in reaching out and establishing relationships with projects related to similar topics such as those addressed by COVINFORM. COVINFORM is now part of two larger networks of similar EU projects. The first cluster called *Sister projects* consists of four projects, including COVINFORM (see here: <https://www.covinform.eu/sister-projects/>). The results of this partnership so far are two successful workshops: *Workshop for Horizon 2020 projects focusing on socio-economic and behavioural consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic* and *Sister Project Workshop: Updates from Horizon 2020 projects focusing on socio-economic and behavioural consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic*. In addition, the Sister projects came together and hosted a joint final conference “Promoting pandemic preparedness: health and policy responses to protect wellbeing and address social inequalities” in Brussels on the 7th September 2023.

Additionally, COVINFORM is part of the PREPARE cluster (PREparedness and resPonse for emergency situAtions in euRopE; see here: <https://www.covinform.eu/prepare/>), which aims to strengthen the response to the ongoing crisis and improve preparedness for future health crises.

Table 4: Related Horizon 2020 Projects

Project	Project Description
SHARE-COVID19	The overarching objective of this project is to understand consequences of the epidemic control decisions to contain the COVID-19 pandemic and to devise improved health, economic and social policies. In our policy recommendations, we strive to make healthcare systems and societies in the EU more resilient to pandemics in terms of prevention, protection and treatment of the population 50+, a most vulnerable part of the population. The project aims to identify healthcare inequalities before, during and after the pandemic; to understand the lockdown effects on health and health behaviours; to analyse labour market implications of the lockdown; to assess the impacts of pandemic and lockdown on income and wealth inequality; to mitigate the effects of epidemic control decisions on social relationships; to optimise future epidemic

Project	Project Description
	control measures by taking the geographical patterns of the disease and their relationship with social patterns into account; and to better manage housing and living arrangements choices between independence, co-residence or institutionalisation.
RESPOND	<p>RESPOND is centred around core questions regarding the short and long-term impacts of the pandemic on mental health and health inequalities on vulnerable groups within the general population, including frontline workers. In the first immediate delivery phase, an impressive set of existing longitudinal datasets are examined for resilience factors and risk factors. Furthermore, the responsiveness of health systems and identification of best practice responses that protect resilience, mental health and wellbeing are assessed in eight EU countries.</p> <p>The long-terms effects are determined of the pandemic and the control measures on demand for (mental) health services in health registers in Sweden, Lombardy and Barcelona and the scalable WHO SH+/PM+ stepped care programmes adapted for COVID-19 will be implemented and evaluated both in frontline workers and vulnerable groups.</p>
PERISCOPE	The overarching objectives of PERISCOPE are to map and analyse the unintended impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak; develop solutions and guidance for policymakers and health authorities on how to mitigate the impact of the outbreak; enhance Europe's preparedness for future similar events; and reflect on the future multi-level governance in the health as well as other domains affected by the outbreak.
unCoVer	unCoVer is a functional network of research institutions collecting data derived from the provision of care to COVID-19 patients by health systems across Europe and internationally. These real-world data allow for studies into patient's characteristics, risk factors, safety and effectiveness of treatments and potential strategies against COVID-19 in real settings, and complement findings from efficacy/safety clinical trials where vulnerable groups, and patients with comorbidities are often excluded. The network will facilitate access to otherwise scattered datasets, and build computational and analytical platforms to streamline studies on risk characterisation, and prediction modelling using standardised pooled data derived from real life practices. It will fill data gaps, unify current initiatives and create downstream exploitation opportunities for researchers and public health strategies to optimise COVID-19 strategies and minimise the impacts of future outbreaks
NO-FEAR	NO-FEAR is a Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European and beyond network of emergency medical care practitioners, suppliers, decision and policy makers to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned. Members of the network will have the opportunity to work together and collaborate to develop a common understanding of the innovation potential that fills operational gaps and pinpoint areas for future research.

Project	Project Description
STAMINA	The goal of the EU-funded STAMINA project is to develop an intelligent decision support platform for pandemic prediction and management. The project will enable national agencies and first responders to anticipate pandemic threats and plan daily efforts to enhance health security. The objectives of the project include the creation of real-time web and social media analytics for the detection of possible disease outbreaks, predictive modelling of pandemic outbreaks and early warning systems. The crisis management part will define the roles of key actors during crisis management and include protection and diagnostic devices for first-line screening. Finally, STAMINA will develop a common operational picture as the main interface that enables coordinated response and demonstrate its application within and across EU borders.
EUNOMIA	EUNOMIA is a fully decentralised, intermediary-free and open-source solution for addressing three key challenges: which social media user is the original source of a piece of information; how this information has spread and been modified in an information cascade; and how likely it is to be trustworthy. EUNOMIA actively encourages democratic citizen participation in content verification by allowing voting on content trustworthiness and influencing the reputation of content generators and sharers. It combines information cascade verification with information trustworthiness scoring, benefitting from blockchain technology to ensure transparency of the scoring process and that information has not been modified in a cascade. It also places emphasis on ensuring that trustworthiness information is communicated transparently and accessibly. EUNOMIA uses social-science based co-design methodologies acknowledging and integrating users' experiences of social media, specifically in how they use and trust the information they interact with.
PANDEM	PANDEM project ended in 2017. Its aim was to contribute to the reduction in the health, socio-economic and security consequences of future pandemics so that society will be better prepared at regional, national, EU and global level. PANDEM assessed pandemic preparedness and response tools, systems and practice at national, EU and global level in priority areas including risk assessment and surveillance, communication and public information, governance and legal frameworks. PANDEM identified gaps and improvement needs leading to the development of viable innovative concepts and analysis of the feasibility of a future demonstration project to strengthen capacity-building for pandemic risk management in the EU.
PANDEM-2	PANDEM-2 implements and demonstrates the most important novel concepts and IT systems to improve the capacity of European pandemic planning and response. Following the PANDEM project (with the same coordinator and many shared partners), PANDEM-2 meets the real-world needs of public health agencies responsible for pandemics ('pandemic managers') and first responders across Europe. PANDEM-2 will enable and demonstrate the capture and integration of pandemic-relevant data from international systems (Go.Data outputs, EWRS, TESSy, etc.), participative surveillance (Influenznet, Studybugs, etc.), from laboratory (next generation sequencing) systems and from social media (Twitter, Reddit). This data

Project	Project Description
	will be accessible and can be analysed via an online dashboard, designed and built to support the specific needs of pandemic managers. Additional high-priority tools for pandemic spread prediction, visual analytics and resources management, including workforce capacity mapping, will improve preparedness and planning, and enable pandemic managers to be as well positioned as possible for a pandemic when it comes.
ESSENCE	ESSENCE aims at transforming the lessons learnt from the COVID-19 in a huge opportunity that exploits technology toward a deep evolution of the services targeting vulnerable populations: non- or pre-frail seniors, and children of the first years of primary school. To contribute to the public health response in the context of the ongoing epidemic, and preparedness for future emergencies, ESSENCE aims at boosting the creation of a new model of home-based care that relies on stimulation, remote monitoring, tele-assistance, and connection between users, families, and professionals.
RECOVER	The overall goal of RECOVER is to understand the COVID-19 pandemic through clinical research in order to transform patient care and public health responses. The EU-funded RECOVER project constitutes a comprehensive research response against SARS-CoV-2, aiming to address patient and public health level interventions. The project builds on the expertise of the FP7 PREPARE project and will undertake clinical studies in primary and hospital care as well as epidemiological and biological investigations and modelling to fill knowledge gaps on SARS-CoV-2 infectivity and transmission. The project's results will strengthen clinical research preparedness for future emerging infectious diseases at a global scale.
RESISTIRE	The overarching aim of RESISTIRE is to understand and work towards individual and societal resilience to the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 30 countries, by designing devising and piloting solutions for improved new policies and social innovations to be deployed by policymakers, stakeholders and actors in the field in different policy domains. As early evidence already suggests, sex and gender influence COVID-19 outcomes in multiple aspects including, differential mortality rates, uneven distribution of care whether due to lockdown measures or as healthcare professionals and rising gender-based violence. It is also known that gender differences intersect with class, age, disability and other inequalities (e.g. race/ethnicity, religion/belief, sexuality, gender identity). Therefore, in meeting the project aim, the project builds around a 'gender+' lens that both highlights gender relations/inequalities and considers how it is related to other inequalities. Analytically, RESISTIRE will draw on an intersectionality-based policy analysis framework, which has emerged to advance understandings of the differential impacts of health policies to produce inclusive and socially just health outcomes. Empirically, RESISTIRE will use the policy domains in the Gender Equality Strategy (EC 2020), fundamental human rights and environmental justice (the latter from the Beijing Platform) to focus the areas for analysis of the impact on inequalities.

Project	Project Description
CO-VERSATILE	To protect European citizens and address the needs of the healthcare sector on short notice, the CO-VERSATILE project aims to prepare Europe for managing pandemics by elevating the adaptability and resilience of the manufacturing sector. The goal is to offer manufacturing and logistics firms readily available and customisable solutions – accessible via a cloud-based marketplace ‘Digital Technopole’ – that enable them to boost the production of vital medical equipment.
COVID-X	COVID-X bridges the gap between the European digital sector and healthcare providers. The program will unlock the full capacity of Artificial Intelligence and Data Technology solutions to overcome COVID-19 Challenges, fast-tracking projects to market and save lives.
EUR3KA	The Eur3ka – EUropean Vital Medical Supplies and Equipment Resilient and Reliable Repurposing Manufacturing as a Service NetwoRK for fast PAndemic Reaction – will be repurposing the manufacturing for vital medical supplies and equipment. Enhancing personal skills, new industrial value chains, service innovation, technological innovation, innovation methodologies, process innovation to fight Pandemics like COVID-19.
LINKS	LINKS (Strengthening links between technologies and society for European disaster resilience) is a comprehensive study on disaster governance in Europe. The overall aim of the LINKS project is to strengthen links between technologies and society for improved European disaster resilience, by producing sustainable advanced learning on the use of social media and crowdsourcing (SMCS) in disasters.
PHIRI	Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (PHIRI) for COVID-19 facilitates research and supports policy making across Europe through the implementation of a research infrastructure to generate the best available evidence for research on health and well-being of populations as impacted by COVID-19.

Project	Project Description
RiskPACC	RiskPACC focuses on increasing disaster resilience across society by closing the so-called Risk Perception Action Gap (RPAG) and aims to provide an understanding of disaster resilience from the perspective of citizens and Civil Protection Authorities (CPAs), identifying good practices led by both citizens and CPAs. RiskPACC will develop a co-creation approach fostering collaboration between various stakeholders and citizens through its seven case studies to build enhanced disaster resilience.
STRATEGY	STRATEGY brings together standardisation bodies, policy makers, technology suppliers and first responders from several EU countries who will collaborate over three years to improve the interoperability of crisis management solutions across the EU.

2.10 Public campaigns

The dissemination strategy will target the general public through awareness raising activities such as targeted campaigns. Online and offline campaigns will be launched to raise awareness of the project's results, the struggles of particular at-risk groups (e.g., gendered impacts of COVID-19 and the rise of domestic violence) and to encourage and promote respect for European values.

M36 Update

The COVINFORM project has been active in engaging with the general public via specific and targeted social media campaigns. These include International Women's Day 2021 and International Women's Day 2022 campaigns, emphasising the project results and spotlighting consortium partners. These campaigns were launched on a specific day (8th of March), whereas the further described campaigns have a long-term nature. COVINFORM has launched two distinctive campaigns on social media to reach a wider audience, bring value, and increase engagement. *The COVID words campaign* shares humorous and unique words used in different European countries in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The second campaign, *the Partner presentation campaign*, aims to introduce all the partners involved in the project and highlight their contributions.

2.11 COVID-19 Knowledge Repository

The project outputs will be available through various channels, including an existing repository on the COVINFORM website. To extend our reach, well-known online research libraries, such as [Zenodo](#), in addition to the EC platform, will also be exploited. Finally, the COVINFORM interactive dashboard will provide functionality to combine data and resources about the COVID-19 pandemic, so that this experience can be used to inform the planning and management of future pandemic situations. It features resources designed to improve the wellbeing and mental health of the population, frontline workers and members of vulnerable groups. The various libraries will draw together COVID-19 resources that were identified as relevant for government and public health representatives, CSOs, NGOs, policymakers, and citizens. See section 2 *Dissemination plan* (Dissemination channels and tools – Project website) for further reference and updates.

2.12 Bi-monthly Reports

Insights into learnings, best practices and challenges in engaging with stakeholders in addressing emergency situations such as pandemics can influence the practices of potential stakeholders. As a part of WP8, COVINFORM created bi-monthly reports for different target groups. These reports were contextualised in relation to the specific scales of government response, changing COVID19 situation (spread, availability of scientific information on the virus) and expected exit trajectories. Reports allowed COVINFORM to be used as a guide in future pandemic situations for improved societal health and wellbeing, particularly among vulnerable members of society. Collaboration with other EU COVID-19 and pandemic projects maximised the exploitation of these reports. It is also hoped reports will help future projects implement successful communication and outreach strategies.

M36 Update

Over the past 3 years, the COVINFORM project has published eighteen bi-monthly reports. The reports are accessible on the COVINFORM project website in the Project Outputs section (<https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/>). The bi-monthly reports published are as follows:

- [Bi-monthly report 01 – COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts](#)
- [Bi-monthly report 02 – COVID-19 vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics & best practices](#)
- [Bi-monthly report 03 – A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic](#)
- [Bi-monthly report 04 – Findings on the Governmental Responses in COVINFORM countries](#)
- [Bi-monthly report 05 – Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 06 – The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers.](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 07 – Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 08 – After two years of pandemic](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report: 09 – After two years of pandemic](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 10 – Socio-economic Impact of COVID-19](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 11 – Resilience in the Systems we live in: 10 European case studies](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 12 – A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lesson learned during COVID-19](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 13 – ‘Closer to death’: thinking about dying in pandemic times](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 14 – “I think we should have shown more empathy as a state” – A critical reflection of the COVID-19 response in Austria](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 15 – Mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and lesson learnt for future crisis](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 16 – COVID-19 Communication Practices, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 17-Migrant women during the pandemic: multiple and intertwined vulnerabilities](#)
- [Bi-Monthly Report 18 – How to build and how to lose trust. Lessons learned and resident perspectives on Crisis communication during COVID-19](#)

3 Dissemination management

This section defines the partners' roles and responsibilities concerning dissemination, as well as the consortium policies and procedures that will be in place for an effective dissemination and the timing of the planned activities.

Responsibilities

TRI coordinated and implemented the dissemination activities; however, all COVINFORM partners were responsible for the online and offline dissemination and communication of project results according to the GA. Resources have been allocated to all project partners for these activities.

Policies and procedures

WP leaders (in collaboration with task leaders) were be responsible for:

- Identifying results suitable for dissemination and communication
- Choosing the most appropriate partner to lead the dissemination of the specific result (most likely the partner generating the result)
- Supporting the responsible partner in identifying the potential audience in collaboration with the WP9 lead partner/s
- Supporting the responsible partner in identifying the appropriate publication channels, in collaboration with the WP9 lead partner/s
- Giving prior notice of ANY planned publication to the Coordinator and all partners at least 45 days before publication. Parties can object within 30 days after receipt of notification (to Coordinator AND Party/ies concerned)

Furthermore, all COVINFORM partners were aware of the following:

- All dissemination and communication materials must comply with the project branding guidelines provided in Annex 1 of this deliverable and include acknowledgement of EC funding (see also D9.2)
- The project coordinator and the WP9 lead partner will provide support to ensure compliance with project branding
- All project deliverables, documents and presentations must be prepared using the provided Word document and PowerPoint presentation templates.
- All partners should obtain consortium approval of all dissemination materials before distribution

3.1 Timeline of dissemination activities

The table below outlines the timeline for COVINFORM dissemination activities and processes, which are broken down into specific tasks, dates and partner responsibilities.

Dissemination/communication activity	Task	Partner	Dates
Dissemination/communication processes	Media contacts search - creation of COVINFORM's PR list	TRI manages, ALL PARTNERS contribute their contacts	M1 – M36
	COVINFORM Stakeholder contact list	TRI manages and ALL PARTNERS contribute	M1 – M36
	Newsletter	SYNYO, all partners contribute	M4-M36 (Every 4 months)
	Establishing a H2020 project cluster for collaboration	All partners	M1-M36
Dissemination activities	Blog posts	TRI manages, ALL PARTNERS contribute	M1 – M36 (At least once a month)
	Attending conferences	ALL PARTNERS	M1 – M36
	Publishing journal articles	ALL RESEARCH PARTNERS	M12 – M36
Monitoring activities	Monitoring impact and dissemination activities	TRI manages, ALL PARTNERS report their dissemination activities using the monitoring spreadsheet	M1- M36 (the monitoring spreadsheet should be updated monthly by all partners)

4 Evaluation and monitoring

One of the main aims of dissemination is to achieve impact. In order to achieve impact and truly make a difference, all dissemination activities will be evaluated for efficacy. This deliverable is a living document (that will be updated if policies and plans change). The M18 update (D9.6) confirms the relevancy of this plan and provides further project updates. All consortium partners are encouraged to keep track of each dissemination activity (and the audience reached whenever possible) as they take place using the provided monitoring spreadsheet. It is important to keep track also of the feedback gathered from the target audience (if applicable) and newly gained contacts are to be listed in the contact repository for further dissemination or exploitation purposes.

We have developed a monitoring tool¹ (Annex 2) for each partner to check and update monthly, but especially during the reporting periods. This will ensure we have relevant up-to-date information to include in the newsletters, promote on social media channels, and update the project website accordingly. The tool consists of an Excel spreadsheet in which the partners will have to specify the details of the dissemination and communication actions performed and the obtained impact (i.e., audience reached with each activity).

When it comes to target audiences and communication/dissemination tools and channels, there is some overlap between the two plans. For this reason, we are going to use the same abovementioned monitoring tool to monitor both dissemination and communication activities. This will avoid confusion as to which spreadsheet must be used; moreover, it will avoid having to collate information from different sources and limit the chances of losing information.

The monitoring tool is designed to meet the European Commission's requests for project promotion and dissemination of results and filling it in is mandatory for reporting. The spreadsheet, along with the guidelines (Annex 3) for filling it in correctly, are available in a specific folder in the collaborative space. Regular reminders will be sent to partners to update the spreadsheet, as the regular use of the monitoring tool will allow us to know if we are achieving impact and how far along, we are in reaching our targets (KPIs).

4.1 Dissemination KPIs

The table below illustrates a list of KPIs for the different channels used in the dissemination activities.

We will monitor these KPIs and keep track of achievements on an ongoing basis by recording the achieved KPIs in the [COVINFORM monitoring spreadsheet](#) that has been distributed to all partners. Moreover, KPIs will be reviewed and monitored at the interim review and at the end of the project and discussed in the COVINFORM consortium meetings and calls as required. The monitoring spreadsheet is currently being reviewed and evaluated to confirm the monitoring of the chosen KPIs is effective and accurate.

¹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1O8n-gN-C74De7eEzsLhTRdZg8OJd6w6s/view?usp=sharing> (only available to the members of the consortium)

Table 6 Dissemination KPIs

Instruments	Target stakeholders	KPIs	Expected impact	M18 results	M36 results
Project website	All stakeholders	At least 4,000 unique visits by M36. M18 Update At least 5500 unique visits by M36.	Interactive and informative impact on interested audiences	4,588 unique visits.	22,466 unique visits
Communication through face-to-face meetings, emails, Skype, invitation to validation workshops	Other projects, Researchers & Academia, Medical Practitioners, Policymakers, NGOs, International Organisations	Engaging with at least 100 stakeholders from at least 6 different countries (not limited to EU).	Provide information to and gather feedback from stakeholders; engage them and influence the outcomes of the project; uptake of press releases by journalists; participation in COVINFORM events	So far, COVINFORM engaged with more than 240 stakeholders from the scientific community by organising workshops.	Through organization of workshops and webinars, and presentations and participation in conferences and other events, COVINFORM has engaged more than 6000 people, of which more than 5000 from the scientific community through conference attendances and presentations, 150 representatives the of civil society, more than 400 policy makers, and more than 400 medical practitioners and first responders

Instruments	Target stakeholders	KPIs	Expected impact	M18 results	M36 results
					through organized workshops.
Newsletters (3 issues per year)	Policymakers, Researchers, Academics	Building a mailing list of 500 individuals/ organisations signed up to receive newsletters by M24 and at least 600 total by M36.	Provide information to stakeholders about the project; engage them and influence the outcomes of the project; participation in COVINFORM events	Four newsletter issues have been sent to the mailing list, which currently has 330 subscribers.	Nine newsletter issues have been sent to the mailing list, which has 371 subscribers. The newsletter is also available on the website
Peer-reviewed journal articles.	Other projects, Researchers & Academia, Medical Practitioners, Policymakers, NGOs, International Organisations	Submission and acceptance for publication of at least 10 articles.	Provide information about key issues raised by COVINFORM to other academics to benefit from the findings.	Two publications written by COVINFORM partners have been submitted and accepted.	7 journal articles and 6 book chapters have been published (a total of 13). One journal article has been accepted and is under revision, 2 other journal articles are submitted. 2 online scientific reports are published.
Blog posts	Other projects, Researchers & Academia, Medical Practitioners, Policymakers,	At least 1 per month. ²	Provide information about COVINFORM research and findings	So far, 24 blogs were published on the COVINFORM website.	42

² The consortium has agreed to start with monthly blog articles in the first phase of the project. Once the project has created first outputs, these numbers will be increased.

Instruments	Target stakeholders	KPIs	Expected impact	M18 results	M36 results
	NGOs, International Organisations, general public				
Presentations at third-party events.	Other projects, Researchers & Academia, Medical Practitioners, Policymakers, NGOs, International Organisations	At least 1 per partner (at least 2 for research partners).	Present COVINFORM results, Build connections and networks between COVINFORM and researchers from other projects and other stakeholders.	At least 6 partners have attended external conferences.	28 conference presentations at 25 conferences, 10 conference attendances, and 38 workshop and other events participations. In some of these events more than one partner participated.
Project Workshops	End-users	At least 3 workshops	Identification and assessment of relevant datasets, indicators and models, and the evaluation of the project outputs.	COVINFORM did not hold any workshops targeting the end-users, as this is planned in later stages.	A total of 6 workshops organized for medical practitioners, and 3 workshops organized for the general public

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has highlighted the activities of the consortium towards the scientific dissemination of the project outcomes as well as (if applicable) an estimation and quantification of the impact of the consortium's scientific dissemination activities. The dissemination strategy is expanded in two directions: 1) towards engaging with key stakeholders (e.g. decision makers, public health officials, medical practitioners), the EC and general public to inform them about the project and its results and 2) Towards paving the way for exploitation and enhancing the potential of the results and how end-users can use them to their benefit. This deliverable has touched on the stages of the dissemination strategy. The three phases include: 1) spanning throughout the project duration and extending beyond it, 2) starting from the creation of general awareness and, 3) concluding with attracting potential supporters and customers/users of the project results.

Annex 1 Achievements

Type of dissemination/ communication activity	Name / Title	Month
Project website	Convinform.eu	M1
Blogposts	COVINFORM: Project on social, behavioural and mental health-related issues kicked off	M1
	Understanding vulnerability through dialogue: two-way dialogue and inclusivity in COVID-19 communication	M2
	First lessons learned from COVID-19 vaccination in Spain	M3
	COVINFORM at the COVID-19 2C sister project meeting	M4
	Quarantine – history repeated	M4
	Why gender matters in the COVID-19 response	M5
	The COVINFORM team – supporting gender equality in EU Research and Innovation	M5
	Red Cross in the COVID-19 pandemic – how Romania handled the outbreak	M5
	The COVAX Facility: the way forward to ensure equitable distribution of COVID-19 vaccines?	M6
	Tackling COVID-19: collaboration for better results	M6
	Joining forces in mitigating risks of the COVID-19 pandemic	M7
	What is the Pandemic Teaching? Vaccines in a changing economic and social context	M7
	Timely, transparent, targeted? Government communications during the pandemic	M8
	One size does not fit all – information seeking during the COVID-19 pandemic in a segregated society	M9
	Red Cross in the COVID-19 pandemic – how Austria handled the outbreak	M10
	Government and the pandemic: structures and response	M10
	18 months of COVID-19 pandemic in Germany	M11
	COVID-19 and mental health: a ‘tsunami’ of problems?	M12
	Pandemic mitigation for everyone: Ethnic differences in Wales	M13
Generation COVID	M14	
Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories	M14	

“Can we at least freak out?” Memes and COVID-19	M16
Nobody told us what to expect (except health professionals and our own simulations)	M17
Italy in lockdown: The ultra-secular battle of laughing to avoid crying	M18
"Un-masking the Mask-Issue": Examining People's Sense-Making Processes and Risk-Cultural Norms regarding Facemasks	M18
Summer holidays 2022: may the COVID be with you (hopefully not)	M22
Monkeypox in the time of COVID-19: Are we on our way to a new pandemic?	M22
New crises, same resilience?	M24
Has COVID-19 changed our cities? Urban planning following the pandemic	M24
Compulsory vaccinations and skipping contact restrictions – differing narratives of freedom in the German middle class	M26
Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?	M26
“Bridging the gap”: The importance of interpersonal risk and crisis communication	M27
Let me explain: why we use intersectionality and complexity theories	M30
How COVID-19 has exposed housing inequalities: insights from Antwerp	M32
Policy and practice mismatches in governmental responses during the COVID-19 pandemic	M33
Delivering inclusive and accessible COVID-19 communication in Birmingham (UK)	M34
Understanding the Systems we Live in: Deconstructing the Systems we Live by	M35
Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part 1	M36
Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part 2	M36
The Challenges of Understanding Covid-Related Risk: Part A	M36
The Challenges of Understanding Covid-Related Risk: Part B	M36
Three Years of COVINFORM: A little glimpse into what we have done	M36
The COVINFORM projects says thank you - a review	M36

Newsletters	Newsletter #1	M4
	Newsletter #2	M8
	Newsletter #3	M12
	Newsletter #4	M16
	Newsletter #5	M20
	Newsletter #6	M25
	Newsletter #7	M31
	Newsletter #8	M36
	Newsletter #9	M36
Conferences (Presented)	6th Society for Risk Analysis Europe Nordic Chapter conference: "Risk Analysis: from Perception to Prediction"	M1
	The Society for Risk Analysis - European Conference 2021	M8
	Gray Rhino, Black Swan or Elephant in the Room: The Role of Crisis Communications in disruptive events.	M12
	SRA 2021: Risk Science and the Policy Interface	M14
	American Association of Geographers Annual Meeting 2022	M17
	La calidad institucional como fundamento de la gestión eficaz y honesta del Plan Nacional de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia en el contexto Covid-19 - Institutional quality as a foundation for effective and honest management of the National Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan in the context of Covid-19	M19
	EASA2022: Transformation, Hope and the Commons	M21
	European Society for Health and Medical Sociology Conference	M22
	AISU 2022	M23
	5th Congress of the Portuguese Psychologists Association	M23
	Netwerksessie integratieonderzoek over de impact van de COVID-19-pandemie op personen van buitenlandse herkomst	M23
	Effects of integration on information seeking. Media use and information seeking among Swedes and immigrants during the COVID-19 pandemic.	M24
	European Public Health Conference 2022	M25
	AISP POPDAYS 2023	M28
	American Association of Geographers Annual Meeting 2023	M29
Population Association of America Annual Meeting	M30	
1st International Summit for Pandemic Management, STAMINA Project	M31	

	Accessing healthcare in the EU: bridging gaps & tackling vulnerabilities	M31
	Dag van de Sociologie "Covid, gentrification and immigrant mental health "	M31
	LIX Scientific Meeting of the Italian Society of Economics Demography and Statistics	M31
	SRA Europe 2022 Lund, Sweden. Palma-Oliveira & Antunes, In search of the Grall: what means an effective risk communication and can we learn from Covid-19.	M32
	ECREA 7th International Crisis Communication Conference: Crisis Communication from a Citizen Perspective – Urban Risks and Crises	M36
	1st session of the permanent group of gender and politics. Spanish Association of Political Science	M36
	ASDR Naturgefahrenstagung 2023	M36
	UNESCO Global Media and Information Literacy Conference	M36
Conferences (Attended)	3rd 'Nicosia Risk Forum' - Regional Collaboration in Societal Safety"	M1
	Emergenza pandemia: quale impatto su natalità e nuove generazioni? Presentazione del rapporto a cura del gruppo di esperti su demografia e COVID-19	M2
	Northern Network of Medical Humanities Congress 2021	M6
	57 Scientific Meeting of the SIEDS (Società Italiana di Economia, Demografia e Statistica)	M7
	Annual International conference Royal Geographical Society with IBG 2021	M10
	Lisbon Forum 2021: Intercultural dialogue in the infodemic era	M12
	Pandemie symposium (Pandemic symposium)	M17
	Royal Geographical Society with IBG 2022, Newcastle	M22
	Northern Network of Medical Humanities Congress 2023	M30
	LSE Commission for Pandemic Governance and Inequalities 2023	M32
Other events (Webinars)	How media and authorities handled the Corona crisis	M0
	NO FEAR webinar on Human Resources management during COVID19	M2
	NO-FEAR webinar on risk communication	M2
	NO FEAR webinar on Supply Chain Challenges during COVID 19	M5
	Minverva Lab Seminars: "COVID-19 and the overlap between job and home responsibilities: new evidence from the U.S. and Italy"	M5
	Scandinavian Pandemic Response: Perspectives on Crisis Communication During the Pandemic in Nordic Countries	M5
	NO FEAR webinar on COVID in children	M6
	The impact of Covid-19 and community responses webinar organized	M6

	NO-FEAR and COVINFORM joint webinar on vaccination hesitancy among healthcare workers	M7
	Webinar for Dept. of occupational health science and psychology and for Academy for health and occupational life, University of Gävle.	M12
	Invited presenter at webinar organized by CRISCOM (civil society organization)	M15
	Webinar with Publicistklubben East (journalists' association)	M16
	Public Health Network Cymru Webinar	M21
Other events (physical and virtual)	COVID-19 2C projects cluster meeting	M3
	Empowering R&I collaboration to respond to the socio-economic challenges of the coronavirus pandemic	M3
	Sharing Marginalised Stories: Pandemic Projects from Swansea	M4
	Invited presenter at "The Media meeting" (Mediemötet), Borås Tidning/UGOT	M7
	Coronavirus and People with Learning Disabilities Study	M7
	Invited presenter at a working meeting at the Swedish Corona Commission	M8
	Pandemic concerns in high trust societies - COVID-19 Lessons learned, organised by Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency	M9
	Gender and COVID-19: Close-to-community providers in fragile settings and vulnerable communities during crisis	M11
	Official Launch of the Welsh Association of Physicians of African and Caribbean Origins (WAPACO)	M13
	Crisis Cooperation 2021 - arranged by West Sweden Region Council	M13
	"Health, Diversity and Covid-19" A conversation with Rohini Mathur (London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine), Orkan Okan (Technical University of Munich) and Katharina Crepaz (Eurac Research)	M15
	Policy Area Secure Steering Group Meeting	M26
	Meeting and discussion results Health Department Municipality of Antwerp and University of Antwerp	M32
	ERA Forum Workshop: R&I gaps, needs and challenges with respect to the twin (digital & green) transitions and their impact on vulnerable workers	M36
Festival della Statistica e della Demografia	M36	
Other events (workshop attended)	Presentation Workshop: "Emotional impact (both professional and personal) in front-line emergency healthcare workers during COVID-19 pandemic"	M6
	CERIS innovation workshop: European Resilience in case of Pandemics 22/04/2021	M6
	Empowering R&I collaboration to respond to the socio-economic challenges of the coronavirus pandemic	M12
	Research to Policy Meeting: COVID-19 social and behavioural studies	M12
	Strategic decision-making during COVID-19 (Hearing Swedish Defense University)	M13

	5th Research to Policy Meeting	M14
	6th Research to Policy Meeting	M17
	Joint final event- ENOTICE, PROACTIVE, PANDEM-2	M32
	MDA internal meeting of the Medical Department	M35
	„CAVE! Weniger vulnerabel in der Krise“	M35
Workshops (organized)	Scandinavian Pandemic Response: Perspectives on Crisis Communication During the Pandemic in Nordic Countries	M5
	Workshop for Horizon 2020 projects focusing on socio-economic and behavioural consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic.	M6
	Workshop for Horizon 2020 projects focusing on socio-economic and behavioural consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic.	M12
	COVINFORM workshop: Two workshops with the participation of MDA staff and volunteers, to present the project's findings and collect practitioners feedback	M32
	COVINFORM workshop: Three workshops with the participation of MDA staff and volunteers, to present the project's findings and collect practitioners feedback	M33
	COVINFORM workshop: Eight organised by SNCR with doctors to discuss the intervention and the challenges during the last years in the COVID-19 context	M32
Publications (scientific for peer-reviewed journals or edited volumes)	Local mortality estimates during the COVID-19 pandemic in Italy	2021
	Understanding vulnerability to inform two-way inclusive COVID-19 communication	2021
	Gender en migratie in tijden van pandemie.	2021
	Migrants as 'vulnerable groups' in the COVID-19 pandemic: A critical discourse analysis of a taken-for-granted label in academic literature	2022
	Meme-ing Accountability: Character Assassination of Austrian and Swedish Politicians and Government Agencies during the COVID-19 Pandemic	2022
	Viral contamination of healthcare policies during COVID19 pandemic in Wales	2023
	Constructing viral subjectivities during the pandemic: women's embodiment in Wales	2023
	Information seeking and repertoires in migrant dense Swedish suburbs during the COVID-19 pandemic	2023
	Watchdogs and Government Megaphones: The dual democratic roles of the news media during the Covid-19 pandemic in Iceland and Sweden.	2023
	Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot	2023
	Evaluación de la gestión de la pandemia COVID-19 en España	2023
	Overcoming vulnerability: resilience strategies amongst migrants in Madrid during the COVID-19 pandemic	2023
	"A beacon of hope": a qualitative study on migrants' mental health needs and community-based organisations' responses during the COVID-19 pandemic in Antwerp, Belgium	2023

	Addressing COVID-19 misinformation and inequalities through communication: Insights from COVINFORM and the WHO Regional Office for Europe	2023
	Migrant women population during the COVID-19 pandemic	2023
	Feeling stuck: The micro-politics of migrant dwelling practices during COVID-19 in Antwerp	In revision, 2023
	Organising Inequality: Viral contamination of healthcare policies during the COVID-19 pandemic in Wales	Submitted, 2023
	To Stay or not to Stay at Home? The Unintended Consequences of Public Health Advice for Older Adults in the context of Covid-19 and Urban Heat.	Submitted, 2023
Publications (not peer-reviewed or non-scientific)	La URJC participa en un estudio europeo sobre el impacto de la COVID-19	M0
	Information in the Times of COVID-19	M1
	COVINFORM: Research project analysing the impact of COVID-19 governmental response on vulnerable groups	M1
	Supporting governmental responses to COVID-19 across Europe	M2
	COVINFORM, un progetto che analizza l'impatto della risposta governativa al COVID-19 sulle popolazioni vulnerabili	M2
	Understanding how COVID-19 exacerbates existing inequalities and vulnerabilities	M2
	Project Overview on the organisation website	M3
	PROJECT OVERVIEW CORonavirus Vulnerabilities and INFORMATION dynamic Research and Modelling	M3
	GLOBAL RESEARCH INTO HOW THE VULNERABLE HAVE BEEN HIT BY OFFICIAL RESPONSES TO COVID-19	M4
	Using data insights to address the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic	M4
	Wie zijn de kwetsbare groepen in de coronacrisis en wat maakt hen kwetsbaar?	M5
	COVINFORM: Analysis of the impact of COVID-19 response on vulnerable groups.	M7
	How vulnerable groups were left behind in pandemic response	M8
White papers, policy briefs, fact sheets & country reports	White papers	
	INCLUSIVE COMMUNICATION IN TIMES OF CRISIS: lessons learned and recommendations from COVID-19 and other CBRNe incidents based on recent COVINFORM & PROACTIVE findings	M14
	White paper on public health responses during the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons learnt and recommendations for policy makers	M36
	Leveraging Public Momentum During a Crisis: Recommendations for Policy and Practice	M36
	Policy Briefs	
	COVID-19 Governmental responses and challenges: The case study of low socio-economic status citizens in Greece	M36
	Addressing Vulnerability and Promoting Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems: A case study comparative analysis of the COVID-19 Pandemic throughout Europe	M36

Healthcare policies during the pandemic: Preventing the spread of COVID-19 or inequality?	M36
STRUCTURES, INSTITUTIONS AND ACTORS IN THE RESPONSE TO THE COVID-19 CRISIS IN SPAIN: Challenges, dilemmas and proposals.	M36
ESTRUCTURAS, INSTITUCIONES Y ACTORES ANTE LA RESPUESTA A LA CRISIS DE LA COVID-19 EN ESPAÑA: Retos, disyuntivas y propuestas.	M36
Community mental health responses for migrants to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic in Antwerp	M36
The impact of COVID-19 on marginalized groups in Greece	M36
Healthcare workers during the pandemic: lessons learned and the way ahead	M36
Policing during COVID-19: The impact of Coronavirus on Law Enforcement Agents	M36
Micro-politics of agency taken by residents living in Antwerp's as a consequence of COVID-19.	M36
"Community" in times of crisis: Perceptions of low-SES women in 10 EU countries	M36
Fact Sheets	
COVINFORM workshop for responders	M36
Emerging vulnerabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic: Findings from the COVINFORM project	M36
EFFECTIVE AND INCLUSIVE CRISIS COMMUNICATION DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: LESSONS LEARNT	M36
Media literacy and COVID-19	M36
Pandemic communication: How can we reach the most vulnerable?	M36
Pandemie Kommunikation: Wie erreichen wir vulnerable Gruppen?	M36
Country Reports	
Public health responses Country reports: Greece	M14
Baseline Austrian Response	
Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot	M23
Opinions on Test, Trace, Protect and COVID-19 vaccination services by BAME and White people in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot	M36
Government responses to COVID-19 and vulnerability in Wales	M33
The COVID-19 pandemic in Wales: Public health governance, preparedness, and vulnerability	M33
Crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic in Wales	M33
The multiplicity of BAME migrant nurses' vulnerabilities in South Wales	M36
Swedish Baseline Report: Public health responses	M36
Public Health Response Austria: COVID-19 Pandemic	M36

	Management and Response of the Covid-19 Pandemic: Austria in Focus	M36
Collaborations with other EU Horizon 2020 Projects	Meeting with RESISTIRE to discuss workshop participation and mutual support for dissemination activities	M4
	Meeting with PERISCOPE to discuss workshop participation and mutual support for dissemination activities	M4
	Meeting with RESPOND to discuss workshop participation and mutual support for dissemination activities	M4
	First organisational meeting to plan a workshop with sister projects	M5
	Second organisational meeting to plan a workshop with sister projects	M5
	Meeting with a H2020 pandemic crisis management for pandemics cluster	M5
	Meeting with PREPARE cluster to discuss collaboration and cross promotion of events	M12
	Meeting with PREPARE cluster to discuss collaboration and cross promotion of events	M14
	Meeting with PREPARE cluster to discuss collaboration and cross promotion of events	M16
	Podcast episode 4 recording with RESISTIRE	M18
	Meeting with sister projects organised by RESPOND to discuss sister project conference 'Promoting Pandemic Preparedness Conference'	M19
	Meeting with sister projects organised by RESPOND to discuss sister project conference 'Promoting Pandemic Preparedness Conference'	M34
Bi-monthly reports	Bi-monthly report 01 – COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts	M3
	Bi-monthly report 02 – COVID-19 Vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics and best practices	M5
	Bi-monthly report 03 – A glimpse of the lessons learned during the COVID-19 pandemic	M7
	Bi-monthly report 04 – Findings on the governmental responses in COVINFORM countries	M9
	Bi-monthly report 05 – Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic	M11
	Bi-monthly report 06 – The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers	M12
	Bi-monthly report 07 – Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19.	M15
	Bi-monthly report 08 – After two years of pandemic I	M17
	Bi-monthly report 09 – After two years of pandemic II	M19
	Bi-monthly report 10 – Socioeconomic impacts of COVID-19	M21
	Bi-monthly report 11 – Resilience in the systems we live in: 10 European case studies	M23
	Bi-monthly report 12 – A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lessons learned during COVID-19	M23

	Bi-monthly report 13 – ‘Closer to death’: thinking about dying in pandemic times	M27
	Bi-monthly report 14 – “I think we should have shown more empathy as a state” – A critical reflection of the COVID-19 respond to Austria	M29
	Bi-monthly report 15 – Mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic and lessons learnt for future crisis	M31
	Bi-monthly report 16 – Communication practices, lessons learned and recommendations	M33
	Bi-monthly report 17 – Migrant women during the pandemic: multiple and intertwined vulnerabilities	M35
	Bi-Monthly Report 18 – How to build and how to lose trust. Lessons learned and resident perspectives on Crisis communication during COVID-19	M36
Press releases	Launching COVINFORM, a project analysing the impact of COVID-19 governmental response on vulnerable groups	<u>M1</u>
	COVINFORM joined forces with its sister projects to increase impact in mitigating the risks of the COVID-19 pandemic	<u>M7</u>
	The Need for Inclusive Communication in Crisis – Findings From European Commission Funded Research	<u>M11</u>
	Minority ethnic groups share experiences of living through COVID with researchers	<u>M28</u>
	The COVINFORM projects says thank you - a review	<u>M36</u>
Distributed flyers	Media COVINFORM	<u>M3</u>
Social media	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TWITTER 2. FACEBOOK 3. LINKEDIN 4. YOUTUBE 5. RESEARCHGATE 	<u>M3</u>
Pitch event	Horizon Europe: Unsere Zukunft gestalten!	<u>M5</u>